

Original Article

Virtual Reality as a New Opportunity to Foster the Emergence of e-Government's Training

Didier Bazalgette (Adjunct Lecturer, SciencesPo, Paris, France) Marc-Olivier Boisset (Centre Georg Simmel, EHESS), Christophe Gaie (SGDSN)

Recent decades have witnessed the rapid emergence of virtual and augmented reality technologies. These technologies offer immersive experiences that transcend reality, providing users with the opportunity to explore virtual worlds and interact with digital content. As the demand for efficient public services and the growth of digitalised offerings continue to rise, there is an increasing need to enhance training methods, especially within the realm of e-Government. This article explores how virtual reality (VR) presents a novel opportunity to accelerate the emergence of e-Government through innovative training approaches.

Expanding the Application of Virtual Reality in Training Scenarios

Virtual reality (VR) emerges as a transformative tool capable of reshaping training dynamics and revolutionising various industries, particularly in the realm of IT applications and capacity building. The strategic implementation of VR warrants consideration in diverse scenarios where conventional training methods fall short. The adaptability and potential for immersive learning experiences offered by VR hold promise in addressing a range of challenges. (Alexander 2021)

Immersive Adoption of IT Innovations

The incorporation of novel IT applications within organisations often encounters resistance due to the steep learning curves associated with technological transitions. The traditional methods of disseminating information through user guides or webinars

can be limiting in terms of user engagement and comprehension. VR, on the other hand, presents a dynamic avenue to effectively introduce intricate IT features. For instance, within interministerial software implementations, the complexity of new features can be seamlessly communicated to multiple stakeholders through immersive VR scenarios (Giraudet de Boudemange & Langlois, 2021). Partners and administrative operators can navigate simulated environments, interact with new software functionalities, and grasp the intricacies in a hands-on manner. This immersive adoption expedites the learning curve, reduces training time, and fosters a more comprehensive understanding of the changes. (Plotzky et al., 2021)

Onboarding in the Virtual Realm

The onboarding process for new team members is often a multifaceted endeavour, encompassing an array of information ranging from operational contexts to team dynamics. VR presents a novel solution to optimise this process and equip new civil servants with a holistic understanding of their roles and responsibilities. By simulating operational contexts, working procedures, team structures, and human resource protocols (Lerner et al. 2020) VR modules provide an initial learning experience that transcends traditional orientations. This approach has dual advantages: it reduces the burden of initial coaching on experienced civil servants and allows them to dedicate their time to more specialised aspects of training. Meanwhile, newcomers are empowered with comprehensive insights into their roles and the broader operational landscape, ensuring a smoother transition and accelerating their integration into the team.

Embracing Complex Learning Objectives

In certain industries, training objectives involve mastering intricate and multifaceted procedures that demand meticulous attention to detail. VR serves as an unparalleled platform for imparting such skills. Consider a scenario in healthcare, where medical professionals must navigate critical decision-making processes in high-stress situations. VR simulations can mirror real-world emergencies, allowing practitioners to make informed choices in a risk-free environment. Similarly, VR can be harnessed to train IT developers in tackling intricate coding challenges or deployment procedures. By immersing learners in complex scenarios and demanding problem-solving tasks, VR nurtures adaptive skills that are transferable to real-world situations.

Overcoming Training Limitations

Traditional training methods often struggle to capture the urgency, emotional nuances, and pressure that typify real-life situations. VR bridges this gap by enabling trainees to experience scenarios as if they were physically present. This facet of VR training not only bolsters engagement and motivation but also fosters emotional connections to the subject matter. From healthcare professionals making time-sensitive decisions

to crisis managers responding to emergencies, the value of training in immersive virtual environments cannot be overstated.

Envisioning the Future of VR Training

The application of VR in training holds immense potential that extends beyond its current use. As VR technology evolves, the range of industries and scenarios that can benefit from its immersive capabilities is set to expand. Collaborative training sessions, real-time simulations of complex scenarios, and cross-disciplinary skill development are all on the horizon. VR stands as a harbinger of transformative learning experiences, poised to empower professionals with the skills and confidence needed to navigate increasingly intricate landscapes. As shown by Barthelmess and Langlois (2018, 2018b, 2018c) the implementation of a new technology in an organization comes with new motivation for the employees.

In the light of these considerations, it becomes evident that the integration of VR into training scenarios offers a paradigm shift in how individuals and organisations approach skill acquisition and development. By harnessing the immersive capabilities of VR, training becomes a dynamic and engaging journey, equipping learners with practical expertise that translates seamlessly into real-world applications.

The Nexus of Stylometry and Virtual Reality for E-Government Training

Within the realm of technological evolution, the convergence of stylometry and virtual reality (VR) emerges as a realm of uncharted possibilities, particularly in the domain of e-Government training. As stylometry—the analysis of linguistic and writing styles—extends its reach into diverse sectors, its integration with the immersive power of VR offers an unprecedented avenue for redefining training paradigms. While VR training in e-Government holds immense potential, the infusion of stylometry introduces an additional layer of innovation. This section embarks on an exploration of the symbiotic potential of stylometry and VR in e-Government training, unveiling novel vistas that reshape the acquisition of skills and knowledge in the digital landscape.

Crafting Distinctive Learning Journeys

Incorporating stylometry into VR-based e-Government training ushers in a personalised and distinctive learning experience. By analysing linguistic patterns and writing styles, stylometry allows training modules to adapt to individual preferences and cognitive tendencies. VR environments can be dynamically tailored based on stylometric insights, ensuring that each trainee engages with content that resonates with their unique learning profile. This personalised approach optimizes comprehension, retention, and skill acquisition, transforming e-Government training into a journey tailored to each participant's cognitive strengths.

Stylometric Identity Verification

Stylometry transcends textual analysis, encompassing the realm of identity verification. The distinctive linguistic patterns of individuals can serve as an additional layer of authentication in VR training scenarios. By integrating stylometric identity verification with VR access, e-Government agencies can ensure that authorised personnel engage with training modules tailored to their roles and responsibilities. This fusion of stylometry and VR fortifies security, enhancing the integrity of training outcomes within the e-Government sphere. (Langlois 2021)

Adaptive Stylometric Micro-Credentials

The fusion of stylometry and VR brings forth the concept of adaptive micro-credentials. Stylometric analysis can identify nuanced changes in writing styles, reflecting the evolution of cognitive processes. As VR training modules are completed, stylometric insights can contribute to the issuance of micro-credentials that reflect not only skill acquisition but also cognitive growth. These adaptive micro-credentials, authenticated through stylometric analysis, stand as dynamic testimonials to the trainee's journey of continuous learning and cognitive expansion within the e-Government domain. (Udagari et al. 2023; Ho 2016)

Stylometry-Enhanced Training Insights

Stylometry's intricate analysis of writing patterns enriches the evaluation of VR training outcomes. E-Government agencies can leverage stylometric insights to gauge not only the depth of skill acquisition but also the nuances of cognitive engagement. This advanced level of analysis provides a comprehensive view of how trainees interact with VR training environments, identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. The integration of stylometry amplifies the precision of training evaluation, facilitating informed decisions on curriculum enhancements and optimisation. (Yadav et al. 2021; Sadav et al. 2020)

Shaping the Future of E-Government Training

As stylometry converges with VR in e-Government training, a realm of untapped potential emerges. The fusion of personalised learning journeys, secure identity verification, adaptive micro-credentials, and enhanced training insights reshapes the very foundation of skills development within the digital landscape. Government agencies, armed with the prowess of stylometry-enhanced VR, step into a future where training becomes an immersive voyage of individual growth, secured authenticity, and data-driven optimisation.

The addition of stylometry and VR opens avenues for unparalleled proficiency, authenticity, and adaptability, guiding e-Government training into a transformative era of cognitive resonance and secure skill acquisition.

Limits and Drawbacks of Virtual Reality

Navigating the Boundaries and Considerations of Virtual Reality Training

The adoption of virtual reality (VR) training introduces a dynamic dimension to skills development and capacity building, yet it is essential to acknowledge that this cutting-edge approach has its inherent limitations and considerations. While the immersive nature of VR offers unprecedented advantages, it is imperative to comprehend the contexts in which it thrives and where its impact may be limited. (Pan et al. 2019)

Complementing, Not Replacing Human Interaction

Virtual reality has the power to transform learning experiences, but it cannot entirely supplant the value of human interaction. Effective collaboration within teams relies on open discussions, comprehension of tacit norms, shared insights, and active participation in decision-making processes. The nuanced dynamics of group synergy often emerge from face-to-face interactions that foster trust, empathy, and seamless communication. While VR can enhance training scenarios, it cannot replicate the nuanced interpersonal bonds that are integral to teamwork. (Feng et al. 2021; Truong et al. 2021 ; Orlandi et al. 2021)

Constructing and Sustaining Interactive Modules

The creation and maintenance of interactive VR modules are endeavours that demand careful planning, dedication, and resources. The process of designing, developing, and refining VR training experiences requires expertise in multiple domains, from content creation to user experience design. Additionally, the dynamic nature of industries and technological advancements necessitates regular updates to ensure that VR modules remain current and relevant. Allocating resources for these endeavours is a critical consideration for organisations embracing VR training. A clear understanding of the cybersecurity issues that could result from the use of VR is also mandatory (Boisset & Langlois 2021)

The Economics of Virtual Reality Equipment

The transformative potential of VR is undeniably captivating, but the investment required in VR equipment can pose financial challenges. Cutting-edge VR hardware, from headsets to accompanying peripherals, often comes at a substantial cost. Equally important is the distribution and allocation of this equipment across various departments and services. Balancing the availability and accessibility of VR hardware within limited timeframes can prove intricate, particularly in organisations with diverse training needs.

Virtual reality training excels in providing structured pathways for skills development, ensuring that trainees traverse predefined scenarios. However, this very strength can also be a limitation. The world of information technology thrives on solving unanticipated problems and navigating uncharted territories. VR modules inherently simplify tasks, potentially overlooking the complexity and fluidity of real-world IT challenges. The adaptability and spontaneity required in certain situations may find limited expression within a VR environment. (Radianti et al. 2020; Di Natale et al. 2020)

While VR simulations offer an immersive environment for learning, the reality of skills development extends beyond the virtual realm. IT professionals, in particular, must grapple with the unpredictable nature of their field, where innovation and problem-solving often transcend the bounds of predefined modules. The true test of expertise lies in the ability to navigate unforeseen challenges and translate theoretical knowledge into actionable insights, a process that occurs in the live IT landscape. (Zhan et al. 2020)

Acknowledging the limits of VR training is a crucial step in optimising its utilisation. Organisations that recognise the contexts where VR excels and where it intersects with the nuances of human interaction can design comprehensive training strategies. Combining VR's immersive learning with mentoring, on-the-job experience, and collaborative problem-solving cultivates well-rounded professionals who thrive in both controlled and unscripted environments. (Xie et al. 2021; Dincelli and Yayla 2022)

In essence, the cautious integration of VR training is vital, aligning its strengths with the intricacies of real-world challenges. As organisations embark on this transformative journey, understanding the delicate balance between VR's advantages and its limitations empowers them to make informed decisions that redefine the landscape of skill development and capacity building. (Xiong et al. 2021)

Conclusion and Perspectives

Virtual reality introduces exciting prospects for enhancing learning and teaching, particularly within civil service IT departments. This article explored immediate applications, such as aiding partners' understanding of IT changes and facilitating the onboarding of new team members. Beyond these applications, virtual reality holds immense potential for accelerating e-Government growth. Future research will delve into additional opportunities and potential applications for citizens. As VR technology

continues to advance, it promises to be a pivotal tool in nurturing the development of e-Government across diverse contexts.

References

Alexander, A., 2021. Virtual onboarding: Lessons from the pandemic. *Public Services Quarterly*, 17(3), pp.208-211.

Barthelmeß, B., Langlois, J., 2018, Digital identity: legal and economic issues, RIPE, 2018.

Barthelmeß, B., Langlois, J., 2018, Development of Blockchain-based infrastructure: Comparative perspectives from Asia and Africa, RIPE

Barthelmeß, B., Langlois, J., 2018, Tokenomics: Emerging strands of research, RIPE, 2018.

Boisset, M.-O., Langlois, J., 2021, An analysis of the Pegasus case: Rise of cyber threats. CRSI, hal-04179574

Di Natale, A.F., Repetto, C., Riva, G. and Villani, D., 2020. Immersive virtual reality in K-12 and higher education: A 10-year systematic review of empirical research. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 51(6), pp.2006-2033.

Dincelli, E. and Yayla, A., 2022. Immersive virtual reality in the age of the Metaverse: A hybrid-narrative review based on the technology affordance perspective, *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 31(2), p.101717.

Feng, Z., González, V.A., Mutch, C., Amor, R., Rahouti, A., Baghouz, A., Li, N. and Cabrera

Giraudet de Boudemange, N., Langlois, J. 2021, Cognitive Stimulation and Virtual Reality: Implications for Teaching and Training in Defence and Security, ICC, 3 :3

Guerrero, G., 2020. Towards a customizable immersive virtual reality serious game for earthquake emergency training. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 46, p.101134.

Ho, T.N. and Ng, W.K., 2016. Application of stylometry to darkweb forum user identification. In *Information and Communications Security: 18th International Conference, ICICS 2016, Singapore*

Hossain, A.S., Akter, N. and Islam, M.S., 2020, January. A stylometric approach for author attribution system using neural network and machine learning classifiers. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computing Advancements* (pp. 1- 7).

Langlois, J., 2021, « When linguistics meets computer science: Stylometry and professional discourse." *Training, Language and Culture* 5, no. 2 : 51-61.

Lerner, D., Mohr, S., Schild, J., Göring, M. and Luiz, T., 2020. An immersive multi-user virtual reality for emergency simulation training: usability study. *JMIR serious games*, 8(3), p.e18822.

Malik, A.A., Masood, T. and Bilberg, A., 2020. Virtual reality in manufacturing: immersive and collaborative artificial-reality in design of human-robot workspace. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 33(1), pp.22- 37.

Orlandi, T., 2021. Reflections on the Development of Digital Humanities. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 36(Supplement_2)

Pan, X. and Hamilton, A.F.D.C., 2018. Why and how to use virtual reality to study human social interaction: The challenges of exploring a new research landscape. *British Journal of Psychology*, 109(3), pp.395-417.

Plotzky, C., Lindwedel, U., Sorber, M., Loessl, B., König, P., Kunze, C., Kugler, C. and Meng, M., 2021. Virtual reality simulations in nurse education: A systematic mapping review. *Nurse education today*, 101, p.104868.

Radianti, J., Majchrzak, T.A., Fromm, J. and Wohlgenannt, I., 2020. A systematic review of immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned, and research agenda. *Computers & Education*, 147, p.103778.

Sadman, N., Gupta, K.D., Haque, M.A., Sen, S. and Poudyal, S., 2020, June. Stylometry as a reliable method for fallback authentication. In *2020 17th International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology (ECTI-CON)* (pp. 660-664). IEEE.

Tashko, R. and Elena, R., 2015. Augmented reality as a teaching tool in higher education. *International Journal of Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education*, 3(1), pp.7-15.

Truong, P., Hölttä-Otto, K., Becerril, P., Turtiainen, R. and Siltanen, S., 2021. Multi-user virtual reality for remote collaboration in construction projects: A case study with high-rise elevator machine room planning. *Electronics*, 10(22), p.2806.

Uddagiri, C. and Shanmuga Sundari, M., 2023, March. Authorship Identification Through Stylometry Analysis Using Text Processing and Machine Learning Algorithms. In *Proceedings of Fourth International Conference on Computer and Communication Technologies: IC3T 2022* (pp. 573-581). Singapore: Springer Nature

Xiong, Jianghao, En-Lin Hsiang, Ziqian He, Tao Zhan, and Shin-Tson Wu. "Augmented reality and virtual reality displays: emerging technologies and future perspectives." *Light: Science & Applications* 10, no. 1 (2021): 216.

Yadav, Shubham, Santosh Singh Rathore, and Satyendra Singh Chouhan."Authorship Identification Using Stylometry and Document Fingerprinting." In *Big Data Analytics: 8th International Conference, BDA 2020, Sonapat, India, December 15–18, 2020, Proceedings 8*, pp. 278-288. Springer International Publishing, 2020.

Zhan, T., Yin, K., Xiong, J., He, Z. and Wu, S.T., 2020. Augmented reality and virtual reality displays: perspectives and challenges. *Iscience*, 23(8).